

A multi-source energy harvesting sensory glove electronic architecture

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Abstract— We present a multi-source energy harvesting architecture, aimed to enhancing the battery last in powering the electronics of a sensory glove, capable to sense fingers movements. In particular, the proposed architecture is based on Radio Frequency, Piezoelectric and Thermoelectric harvesters. The glove is equipped with flex sensors and built-in electronics which includes a microcontroller and a transmitter. The overall harvesting system was built and tested as a prototype discrete element board, that is interfaced with an external microcontroller and a radiofrequency transmitter board. Measurement results demonstrated a meaningful improvement in battery operation life time up to 22%, considering different operating scenarios.

Keywords—Energy harvesting, power management, Sensory glove

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays energy recovery from environmental power sources (harvesting) is an innovative and appealing way to capture and store energy for small, wireless autonomous devices, like those used in wearable electronics and wireless sensor network systems [1-9]. The number of “free” energy feeders is daily increasing thanks to the huge number of broadcasted TV channels, wi-fi hot spots accesses, mobile telephone infrastructures, etc. Nevertheless, all these signals have absolutely non-constant values of power, depending either on locations or on the environment. Meaningfully, batteries represent the most relevant source for compact, low-power systems, portable electronic devices, in the market. Unfortunately, the Achilles heel of the battery still remains its time duration. This problem represents also a limit for further expansion of a highly potential market because of their replacement and encumbrance requirements.

Regardless of notable efforts dedicated to developing power harvesting techniques to scavenge power either from the environment or from the human body, these techniques are not yet considered reliable and feasible, but research is steadily progressing [10]. Currently, Energy Harvesting (EH) and its applications, for the sensory glove [11-13] in general,

and for array of sensors in particular, are more and more gaining in interest [14, 15]. Specifically, the power-source required by the sensory glove can be harvested by means of different energy sources, depending on the application and the environment, such as electromagnetic, solar, thermal, acoustic, vibrational, etc.. Nevertheless, one of the main issues regards the portability and the power-supply autonomy of the whole system, considering the as-lower-as possible encumbrance and weight, and including electronic circuits, which integrates a relatively high-demanding wireless transmission system. Unavoidably, the current approach is based on large-size batteries and wired systems, which are, indeed, unpractical and uncomfortable. Therefore, here we considered the development of an unwired, size- and weight-reduced system which, exploiting energy harvesting techniques, can allow the gathering of “environmental” energy so to reduce its battery power-supply requests.

Our idea was to extend the battery durability integrating two different power-gathering solutions. This is not a trivial matter, since both of them have to be simultaneously available and to furnish an approximatively equal amount of energy.

In this perspective, here we propose an integrable architecture able to extend the battery duration of a battery powered sensory glove by gathering energy directly from the human heat, the vibrations and the available surround RF energy.

The proposed multi-harvester system integrates Thermo-Electric Generators (TEGs) (that can be applied on the human forearm), stacked piezoelectric (PZT) disks, placed in the heel of a shoe, so to scavenge energy from the pressure generated by feet during walking or a running session, and RF dual band circuitry to capture energy from the available surrounding RF power.

The architecture was tested as an integration of preliminary prototype discrete element boards, mainly composed of an external microcontroller and a commercial RF transmitting board. The measurement results demonstrated an extended battery operation life time up to 22%, considering different operating scenarios.

II. MATERIALS

Human hands are fundamental to interact with the surroundings and to communicate too. Therefore, the possibility to dynamically measure the fingers and hand movements can be beneficial for a number of applications, such as sign language recognition [11], interacting with serious game for training or motor impairment rehabilitation [16], for the evaluation of surgical gesture [12], etc. The measure of the fingers and hand movements can be advantageously performed by means of a sensory glove [14]. Typically, the sensory glove is made by a light, elastic glove with flex sensors embedded [13], which allows providing of electric signals analog to fingers and hand movements [14]. Generally speaking, the hand motor capabilities have been modeled by 27 degrees of freedom (DOFs) [16, 17], so to take into account of both flexion/extension of the joints of the fingers and rotation/bending of the wrist. However, for usual applications, we can limit to a sub-set of DOFs. In particular, here we consider a combination of 14 flex sensors and one inertial measurement unit (IMU) (Figure 1), which already demonstrated good performances in terms of repeatability and reproducibility of the measures [18-21].

Evidently, practical reasons impose a wireless transmission system of the sensory glove. Therefore, here we propose a sensory glove with wireless connectivity as represented in Figure 2. In particular, the overall system includes a multi-harvester block, a RF commercial transmitting block driven by a microcontroller and a remote receiving block too. The real case application scenario is represented as in Figure 3. We realized the transmitting and receiving blocks by means of commercial discrete components.

Figure 1: Sensory glove with 27 DOF

Figure 2: The complete system block scheme

Figure 3: Data glove acquisition and visualization process

III. METHODS

The proposed system architecture is shown in Figure 4. It includes three different harvesters terminated with a Schottky diode so to avoid reverse current flow.

Figure 4 shows the overall block scheme for the battery life enhancement, that is able to reduce the overall current coming from the battery by exploiting the harvested energy. To be specific, the DC/DC converter LTC3107 (ex Linear Technology, now Analog Devices) is used to gather energy from a set of TEGs, and to arbitrate the power path with the battery; LTC3588 (by the same company) AC to DC converter is used to convert the energy obtained by the human walk; the DC/DC LTC3108 is used as a Voltage converter coming from the RF path of the multisource harvester.

Figure 4: Blocks representing the multi-harvesting system. It includes a thermal, pressure and RF energy harvesting paths, connected to a power management block

The energy coming from the human heat is collected by means of a set of standard 3cm x 3cm Peltier cells. The cells were arranged in series connection as depicted in Figure 5a. This is because of the distribution of the heat along the human arm, which is not uniform, thus each cell cannot provide exactly the same output voltage and a parallel connection could cause a dispersion current between cells, reducing the overall efficiency. In this configuration, a conducted test campaign proved that the TEG cells can provide an output voltage ranging from 20mV (static arm and rest condition) to 200 mV (fast movement). A 1:100 transformer is used for the fly-back converter, integrated in the LTC3107, in order to allow the DC-DC conversion, so to guarantee its functionality with input voltages as low as 20 mV. Regarding the piezo harvesting branch (Figure 5b), we adopted a parallel configuration of multiple stacked piezoelectric disks. Finally, for the RF branch, a multichannel harvester operating at 936MHz and 2.4GHz with a high and low incoming power path, was implemented [8].

The LTC3108 step-up topology operates from input voltages as low as 20mV by using a small step-up transformer. In this case a commercial multiband antenna furnished by *TAOGLAS*, named TG.31.8112W, was adopted (Figure 5c). Two different discrete prototype boards (Figure 5d for TEG, PZT and Figure 5e for RF path), with discrete components mounted both on the top and bottom layer of a board, were designed, fabricated and assembled.

IV. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

Concerning the standalone paths, the TEG harvester shows a relatively high conversion efficiency at lower equivalent resistive loads, while the minimum start-up voltage increases as the current requirements rises as well. This problem is mitigated with the introduction of the battery, thus enabling the power path management, which provides as much current as the TEGs can provide, by varying the equivalent load seen from the TEG harvester. Figure 6 summarizes the different performances with different loads. The curve shows an efficiency peak value at about 10KOhm of equivalent resistive

load. Figure 7 illustrates the overall PZT harvested available power, considering an equivalent resistive load and a 70kg human walking at 1km per hour. In this case the maximum power transfer condition is achieved with a 1kOhm of equivalent resistive load. Finally Figure 8 shows the multichannel RF path conversion efficiency. The long-dashed curve depicts the efficiency for the low-power RF channel (-20 dBm to 5 dBm), while the dotted curve shows the medium-power efficiency (5 dBm to 20 dBm) of the RF to DC converter. The combination of the two channels results in an extended high efficiency for a wider incoming RF power range.

In order to test the capabilities of the whole harvesting system, a low-power acquisition and transmission board was implemented (Figure 3). The system includes an ARM Cortex M0 (by Microchip) and a Si4463 transceiver (by Silicon Labs) set up to short 5 dBm transmission range. The overall current is about 4 mA in idle mode, and as-low-as 10 mA in transmission mode. According to [9], the acquisition and transmitting rate can be reduced to 15 ms and 5 ms for a mean current consumption of 5.5 mA, respectively. In this perspective, results demonstrate how the harvester can extend the measured battery life-time up to a noticeable 22%

Figure 5: a) TEG Harvester; b) PZT Harvester; c) RF antenna; d) Electronic board of the TEG and PZT Harvester; e) Electronic board of the RF Harvester

V. CONCLUSION

A sensory glove system, supply-power enhanced by means of multi-source power harvester architecture is presented. The ensemble of a prototype board, which integrates circuitry to scavenge energy from RF, of a Thermo-Electric Generators and of piezoelectric disks, was tested, demonstrating the feasibility towards low supply-powered IC applications.

Figure 6: TEG energy conversion efficiency vs Load

Figure 7: Overall piezo harvested power

Figure 8. RF path conversion efficiency [8]

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